

Comparative assessment of anti-Free Radical and antibacterial properties of methanolic extracts of *Callistemon lanceolatus* leaf extracts from Chhattisgarh and Himachal Pradesh region.

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Abstract

Callistemon belongs to the Myrtaceae family, which has roughly 50 different kinds of shrubs. Australia's east and southeast are home to the majority of these species. One of these, *Lemon bottlebrush*, or *Callistemon lanceolatus* (Sm.) Sweet, a significant medicinal plant that has been used for a long time for curing a variety of illnesses. Many tropical and subtropical environments are home to *C. lanceolatus*. Triterpenoids, flavonoids, fatty acids, and phenolic compounds are only a few of the many different chemical components found in this plant.

In our research we used *C.lanceolatus leaf* sample from two different state for comparative study in two parameters first antibacterial by using *E.coli* and *S.aureus* and second anti free radical property by using DPPH(2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) assay. In our research, result was more effective for Himachal Pradesh leaf sample, in Antioxidant assay light purple color absorption appearance formed with high antioxidant property, dark color appearance formed with low antioxidant property in chhattisgarh sample and in antibacterial property testing, zone of inhibition was much larger as compare to chhattisgarh leaf sample it means it may be possible Himachal pradesh leaf sample contains high amount of secondary metabolites.

Key word

Callistemon lanceolatus, *E.coli*, *S.aureus*, DPPH

Introduction

Callistemon lanceolatus belongs to the Myrtaceae family, which has roughly 50 distinct species of shrubs. Australia's east and southeast are home to the majority of these species. *Callistemon lanceolatus* is also known as lemon bottlebrush, is a significant medicinal plant that had long been utilized to treat several ailments.

Flavonoids, triterpenoids, fatty acids, as well as phenolic compounds are only a few of the many different chemical components found in this plant. Numerous biological characteristics, like antioxidant, antiproliferative, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antibacterial, as well as insecticidal effects, have been described for *C. lanceolatus* extracts.

In this research, our goal is to study Himachal pradesh and chhattisgarh region's leaf sample and their comparative study for different parameter like antibacterial and antioxidant properties by using methanolic extract of *Callistemon lanceolatus*.

Leaf sample of *Callistemon lanceolatus* from Himachal Pradesh region, were collected during our industrial trip which was held on 08/01/2025 at manali.

Related work

(a) Miscellaneous activities

[Ravichandran et al.\(2015b\)](#) The greatest way to obtain plant-based medicinal qualities is through the environmentally friendly process of silver nanoparticle formation. Because *Callistemon lanceolatus* contains many secondary metabolites, so its silver nanoparticle has more effective function to kill many disease causing microbes.

(b) diabetic rats.

Anti-inflammatory activity

Immune-mediated illnesses, diabetes, cancer, allergies, and cardiovascular dysfunction are all mainly triggered by uninhibited inflammatory mediator synthesis. Inflammatory-mediated disorders are increasingly being treated with plant extracts and secondary metabolites. [Sudhakar et al. \(2004\)](#) investigated anti-inflammatory as well as antinociceptive characteristics of *C. lanceolatus* leaf essential oil employing in vivo animal models.

(c) Antioxidant assay

[Kumar et al. \(2011a\)](#) Methanol extracts of *C. lanceolatus* had been investigated for their capacity as antioxidants. It was discovered that extract exhibited an antioxidant activity by nitric oxide, superoxide, scavenging hydroxyl radicals, as well as DPPH₂, (2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl). In addition to their capacity to safeguard against pBR322 plasmid DNA, methanol extracts from *C. lanceolatus* leaves demonstrated significant DPPH radical scavenging activity exhibiting IC₅₀ value 155µg/ml. ([Kumar et al., 2015](#)).

(d) Antidiabetic activity

[Kumar et al. \(2011a\)](#) examined antidiabetic effects of a methanol extract made from *C. lanceolatus* leaves in rats with diabetes caused by streptozotocin. Both streptozotocin-induced as well as glucose-loaded diabetic rats demonstrated a notable drop in blood glucose levels after receiving methanol extract orally for 21 days. Methanol extract-treated group showed higher levels of serum insulin as well as HDL (high-density lipoprotein) cholesterol as well as lower levels of serum cholesterol, blood glucose, as well as triglycerides when compared to diabetes control group. Rats having alloxan-induced diabetes, oral treatment of *C. lanceolatus* leaf methanol extract's ethyl acetate fraction significantly reduced blood glucose levels as well as enhanced liver and kidney function.

Experimental details ,methods ,materials

Antioxidant assay

Antioxidants shield cells from free radicals formation, including superoxide, peroxides, oxygen, hydroxyl radicals, and reactive oxygen species. In our research *Callistemon lanceolatus*'s antioxidant activity was evaluated utilizing DPPH free radical scavenging activity.

Potential of stable free radical molecule DPPH, which has purple hue, to be reduced to generate yellow diphenylpicryl hydrazine provided the basis for DPPH antioxidant action colored substance when an antioxidant is present. An increase in free radical scavenging activity is indicated by a decrease in DPPH solution's optical density.

The standard was ascorbic acid, while the control was a DPPH solution. MS-Excel 2010 was used for the statistical analysis, and Mean \pm SE was used to examine the standard errors in each sample.

S.No	Vol. of Extract (ml)	O.D. (517nm) of leaf extracts		
		Methanol (Himachal pradesh)	Methanol (Chhattisgarh)	Ascorbic acid
1.	0.000	0.270	0.125	0.39
2.	0.020	0.24	0.200	0.25
3.	0.040	0.275	0.150	0.24
4.	0.060	0.24	0.160	0.18
5.	0.080	0.085	0.090	0.10
6.	0.100	0.170	0.025	0.1

Table 1.1 Comparative DPPH estimation through UV visible spectroscopy for Methanol extracts of *Callistemon lanceolatus* from the regions of Chhattisgarh and Himachal Pradesh .

Methanol extracts of *Callistemon lanceolatus* from the regions of Chhattisgarh and Himachal Pradesh were discovered to have antioxidant activity. The presence of antioxidants may be the cause of bioactive compounds found in plants, such as flavonoids and phenol. Flavonoids and other free hydroxyl groups are necessary for plants to have antioxidant action (Mensor et al., 2001).

The antioxidant property was examined by DPPH method using ascorbic acid as standard. we used sample mixture of 1ml plant sample with 3ml methanol for testing antioxidant assay.

Graph 1.1: Using the DPPH technique to demonstrate the antioxidant activity of *Callistemon lanceolatus* leaf extract.

Fig1.1 showing DPPH assay for different samples, where a and b are chhattisgarh leaf sample, c and d are Himachal Pradesh leaf sample and e is ascorbic acid

Antibacterial activity

For comparative antibacterial activity here two different bacterial samples were used, *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) *Staphylococcus aureus*, which are disease causing microbes. we used Disc diffusion method for antibacterial property analysis.

Particular to the Disc Diffusion Method A cotton swab or spreader was used to distribute the bacterial and fungal samples that were removed from the incubated petri plate. The Disc Diffusion Method involves first creating a small, spherical disc out of Whatman filter paper number one, and then using forceps to dip each disc into an extract of our collected leaf samples. Using a marking pen, the petri plates were divided into 2 equal sections on the outside. in one side 3 different concentration of himachal pradesh sample were used in another side chhattisgarh leaves sample were used, while in center we used a single disc for a comparison analysis with the commercial antibiotic streptomycin.

Fig1.2 :Comparative antibacterial activity by using disc diffusion method, here a,b,c are himachal pradesh leaf extract and d,e,f are showing chhattisgarh leaf extract.

Table 1.2 In following table three concentrations (0.2ul, 0.4ul, 0.6ul) of extract were used for evaluation and zone of inhibition was measured in mm.

S.no.	Leaf extracts with methanol solvent	Zone of inhibition of leaf extract					
		<i>Escherichia coli</i> (<i>E. coli</i>) (mm)			<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (mm)		
		0.2ul	0.4ul	0.6ul	0.2ul	0.4ul	0.6ul
1	From Himachal pradesh region	8	9	12	5	8	10

2	From chhattisgarh region	6	7	11	3	4	9
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Observation and Result

Our findings for antimicrobial activity of Himachal Pradesh region leaf sample displayed the most significant zone of inhibition towards *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) (12mm) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (10 mm).

Methanol extract has been studied employing simple agar well diffusion approach by using among three different concentrations (0.2 µl, 0.4 µl, 0.6 µl), maximum zone of inhibition was obtained at 0.6 µl sample. It means Himachal Pradesh leaf sample has more potent quality to kill microbes as compared to Chhattisgarh leaf sample.

For antioxidant assay in Himachal Pradesh leaf sample, antioxidant activity was found more higher than Chhattisgarh region leaf sample, may be the secondary metabolites concentration was higher in Himachal Pradesh leaf sample. It means Himachal Pradesh leaf sample has more antioxidant property to reduce the formation of free radicals, as compared to Chhattisgarh leaf sample.

Discussion :

We collected leaf sample in our Himachal Pradesh industrial trip and another from our state Chhattisgarh, and we found the best result in Himachal Pradesh region leaf so high amount of secondary metabolites can be identified from that sample, which can be used in medicinal field to cure many diseases.

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Discipline

Biotechnology

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